

Experiences in how RSE community identity leads to improved research software practices

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Research software once

- Research software once was a heroic endeavor, particularly in HPC
- My advisor created his own standalone simulation software in the 1960/70s
 - Depended on compilers and operating systems (and later PVM, then MPI), but otherwise had no dependencies
- When I started work with him (1987)
 - Transferred from student to student by hand (email/floppy); he kept the “master”
 - Coding practices were what he said; some pushback from students led to some changes
 - Installation was compiling, typically with a hand-typed command
 - Documentation was very few comments in the code to identify sections, lots of papers
 - Testing was mostly high-level replication of results known by theory

Research software today

- Most research software today is a social endeavor
- Most software depends on other software and is developed/maintained by multiple people
- We have best/“good enough” practices for testing, documentation, installation, version control, issues, PRs
- **Q: How do these practices form and become accepted in different contexts?**
- Research software engineering (RSEng) and research software engineers (RSEs) becoming accepted parts of the research software endeavor
- **Q: What’s the role of RSEs in creating, adapting, and infusing these practices?**
- Let’s look at communities, projects, and groups

1 - Research software community

Journal of Open Source Software (JOSS)

- JOSS started to fill a gap: to better recognize software contributions
 - By finding a way to fit software into current (paper/book-centric) system
- Solution
 - Make it as easy as possible for authors to write software papers based on existing software documentation
 - Main purpose of JOSS paper is to enable citation credit to be given to authors of research software
 - A JOSS paper should be seen as equivalent to an accepted paper elsewhere
- JOSS reviews
 - On GitHub, open, non-anonymous, checklist-driven, collaborative
 - Editor's job is to find reviewers, and to help them and author come to agreement

JOSS review criteria

- Some criteria have guidance
 - Installation
 - API documentation
 - Community guidelines
 - Automated testing
- These have levels, e.g., for installation
 - Good: The software is simple to install, and follows established distribution and dependency management approaches for the language being used
 - OK: A list of dependencies to install, together with some kind of script to handle their installation (e.g., a Makefile)
 - Bad (not acceptable): Dependencies are unclear, and/or installation process lacks automation

JOSS as an element of RSE community

- JOSS practices (these levels) have influenced reviewers and developers in terms of what's good and what's minimally acceptable
- Similar to rOpenSci's influence in the R community
- Cultures change based on rules and incentives
- JOSS provides rules, and at a high-level, tries to nudge incentives
- Over time, community changes, and JOSS levels also change (stricter)
- Many JOSS authors and reviewers (and editors) are RSEs
- If software was cited directly, JOSS papers wouldn't be needed, but JOSS reviews and JOSS (and RSE) community would still be important in shaping values

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2 - Research software projects

Parsl: parallel programming in Python

Apps define opportunities for parallelism

- Python apps call Python functions
- Bash apps call external applications

Apps return “futures”: a proxy for a result that might not yet be available

Apps run concurrently respecting dataflow dependencies. Natural parallel programming!

Parsl scripts are independent of where they run. Write once run anywhere!

```
pip install parsl
```

```
@python_app
def hello ():
    return 'Hello World!'

print(hello().result())
```

Hello World!


```
@bash_app
def echo_hello(stdout='echo-hello.stdout'):
    return 'echo "Hello World!"'
```

```
echo_hello().result()
```

```
with open('echo-hello.stdout', 'r') as f:
    print(f.read())
```

Hello World!

Parsl history

- Supported by an NSF SI2 award from 2016-2022 (5 years + 1-year NCE)
- Started as an idea in 2016, based on previous project Swift (<http://swift-lang.org/main/>)
 - Basically asked if we want to do the same thing – a simple tool (language/runtime) for fast, easy scripting on big machines – today, what would we do
 - One person did some exploration/proof-of-concept – it worked
 - Build the initial usable system, was the main developer, did things the way they wanted
 - Once a second developer became active, needed to agree on and define/document processes
 - As we moved to a more open community project (2-4 FTEs/year of developers funded, and 73 contributors), these processes became more important
- Open source
- Released version 1.0 in 2020, now releasing weekly
 - Focus since v1.0 mostly maintenance rather than adding new features
- Funded development team: 2-4 people/FTEs per year
 - Current funding includes new NSF & CZI awards, contributions from projects that require Parsl

Parsl processes

- How to make design/architecture decisions?
- What code style to use?
- What testing is sufficient?
- What documentation is sufficient?
- How to engage with and support users?
- What properties do contributions and changes need to have?
- How do contributions and changes get accepted?
- How to encourage/develop contributors?
- How to mix CS research and software product development?
- Who writes papers and who is listed as co-authors?
- All of the answers have changed over the life of the project

Parsl team/community

- We made specific decisions on these processes; alternative decisions could have been equally valid
- These practices are part of what makes the development team a community
- As new developers come in, there's often discussion about these practices and if they can/should be improved
- Many of these developers are RSEs, and some are undergrad/grad students or faculty
- All bring in ideas, new ideas mostly from RSEs and students
- Parsl processes impact others
 - All contributors learn from Parsl; impacts their future projects
 - RSEs also use this to influence their groups and larger RSE community
 - Students may influence other students; some students will become RSEs

3 - Research software groups

How a local RSE organization starts

A software developer hears about RSEs, and realizes they are one

- Talk about this with colleagues, leading to informal community
- Formalize the community
 - Mailing list, slack, lunches, meetings

Or perhaps software developers group together to more effectively manage changing projects/staffing needs over time and provide some semblance of a career path in a soft-funded environment

- Formalize a group (if enough are in a unit, e.g., department, IT, research)
 - Develop mission, working internally and with stakeholders
 - Discuss institutional funding support for the group (full, partial, none)
 - Create career path, including how they fit into formal HR positions

Or perhaps an administrator hears about RSEs, and realizes they either have some or should

- To compete with other universities
- To recognize work done within the company
- They formalize a group (e.g., in a department, IT, research center)
 - Stakeholders develop mission
 - Determine institutional funding support for the group (full, partial, none)
 - Create career path, including how they fit into formal HR positions
 - Hire leader and group members (or reorganize existing staff)

- Community or group and its members joins international, national, local RSE groups
- Share experiences, learn from each other
- Talk about work with HR, create proper official roles
- Everyone lives (and works) happily ever after
 - Note: a group can get too big, then needs to rethink funding, structure, ...

RSE group & community models

- RSEs work on multiple projects, each with its own choices of practices
- But multiple RSEs in a group with multiple projects means these RSE groups can collectively think at a metalevel
 - What sets of practices are good
 - Which ones from that set could be used in a new project
- RSEs also communicate across local RSE groups via national RSE organizations (e.g., US-RSE)
- And influence their organization and others
 - RSEs work with faculty, staff, and students in their organization and those on multi-institution projects
 - And infuse good practices into these parts of the community

Conclusions

- All practices, including research software practices, are tied to the communities that perform them
- RSEs are increasingly leading the research software development community
- They often are the point where new practices become accepted and then disseminated
- This happens in projects, RSE groups, and the community as a whole
- Want to change practices quickly? Get RSEs to adopt them by convincing champions who are RSEs

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